

Hepatic Dysfunction in Patients of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract:

Background: Hepatic dysfunction is a common yet often overlooked complication in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). The interplay between T2DM and liver diseases such as non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) is complex, with insulin resistance playing a pivotal role in the pathogenesis. This study aimed to evaluate the prevalence and clinical characteristics of hepatic dysfunction in patients with T2DM.

Methods: Total 100 patients with T2DM aged 15 years and above were included. Patients were assessed through detailed history, physical examination, liver function tests (LFTs), and ultrasonography. Inclusion criteria were based on the American Diabetes Association's diagnostic standards. Patients with other chronic liver diseases or on specific hepatotoxic medications were excluded. Data were analyzed to determine the prevalence of hepatic dysfunction and its correlation with diabetes duration and control.

Results: The study population comprised 42% males and 58% females, with a mean age of 51 years. Hepatic dysfunction was prevalent in 34% of patients, indicated by increased hepatic echogenicity on ultrasound. Abnormal LFTs were observed in 45% of patients, with significant elevations in serum bilirubin, AST, and ALT. Hepatomegaly was present in 25% of patients. The risk of hepatic dysfunction increased with the duration of diabetes, being highest in those with diabetes for more than 10 years. Controlled diabetes was associated with a lower prevalence of hepatic dysfunction.

Conclusion: Hepatic dysfunction is highly prevalent in patients with T2DM, particularly those with long-standing disease. Early detection through regular screening and effective management of diabetes can mitigate the risk of progression to advanced liver disease.

Recommendations: Routine screening for hepatic dysfunction should be integrated into the management of T2DM, especially for patients with a longer duration of diabetes or poor glycemic control. Lifestyle modifications and pharmacological interventions should be considered to manage NAFLD and NASH effectively.

Keywords: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Hepatic Dysfunction, Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease, Liver Function Tests, Insulin Resistance.

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Introduction

Hepatic dysfunction is a significant complication in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), with an increasing prevalence and clinical importance in recent years. Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and its more severe form, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), are particularly common among diabetic patients. NAFLD, characterized by excessive fat accumulation in the liver in the absence of significant alcohol consumption, affects up to 70% of individuals with T2DM. This condition not only complicates the clinical management of diabetes but also contributes to increased morbidity and mortality due to liver-related and cardiovascular complications [1].

The interplay between T2DM and NAFLD is complex and multifaceted. Insulin resistance, a hallmark of T2DM, plays a central role in the pathogenesis of NAFLD. Insulin resistance leads to increased lipolysis and free fatty acid flux to the liver, promoting hepatic steatosis. Concurrently, hyperinsulinemia and hyperglycemia contribute to lipotoxicity, oxidative stress, and inflammation, which can progress to NASH and fibrosis. These pathological processes highlight the bidirectional relationship between T2DM and NAFLD, where each condition exacerbates the other [2].

Recent studies have underscored the importance of early detection and management of hepatic

dysfunction in diabetic patients. Screening for NAFLD in patients with T2DM, especially those with obesity and metabolic syndrome, is crucial for timely intervention. The current guidelines recommend a multistep approach for NAFLD screening, incorporating non-invasive tests (NITs) such as transient elastography and biomarkers, followed by imaging techniques like ultrasound and MRI for confirmation. This approach aims to identify patients at risk of advanced fibrosis and cirrhosis, who may benefit from specialized care [3].

Therapeutic strategies for managing hepatic dysfunction in T2DM primarily focus on lifestyle modifications, including weight loss, dietary changes, and physical activity. Pharmacological interventions are also being explored, with some showing promise in reducing hepatic steatosis and improving liver histology. For instance, studies have indicated that medications such as pioglitazone and GLP-1 receptor agonists may have beneficial effects on NAFLD in diabetic patients. However, more research is needed to establish their long-term efficacy and safety [4].

The prevalence of hepatic dysfunction in T2DM and the potential for severe liver-related outcomes necessitate a proactive approach in clinical practice. Understanding the pathophysiology, implementing effective screening protocols, and optimizing therapeutic interventions can significantly improve patient outcomes. As research advances, integrating novel biomarkers and therapeutic targets will be essential in managing this challenging comorbidity [5].

This study aimed to evaluate hepatic dysfunction in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Methodology

Study Design: An observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Department of Medicine at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, from May 2017 to February 2018.

Study Population: A total of 100 patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus type 1 and type 2, aged 15 years and above, were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients were diagnosed with diabetes mellitus based on the American Diabetes Association (ADA) criteria:

1. Fasting blood glucose level ≥ 126 mg/dl (7.0 mmol/L) on two separate occasions.
2. Random plasma glucose level ≥ 200 mg/dl (11.1 mmol/L).

3. Blood glucose level ≥ 200 mg/dl (11.1 mmol/L) two hours after ingestion of 75 g glucose.

Exclusion Criteria

- Alcohol intake > 20 g/day (women) or > 30 g/day (men).
- Chronic liver disease due to other causes (hepatitis B, hepatitis C, drug-induced, autoimmune diseases, decompensated cirrhosis).
- Overt cardiac dysfunction, recent stroke, or pregnancy.
- History of using Antiarrhythmics, Antibiotics, Anticonvulsants, Antivirals, Antifungals, Antiandrogens, Antidepressants, Antihypertensives, Antipsychotics, Diuretics, Oral hypoglycemics, Oral contraceptives.
- History suggestive of inflammatory bowel disease, jejunioileal bypass, or total parenteral nutrition.

Data Collection

Patients were evaluated through a detailed history and thorough physical examination, including personal antecedents like history of alcohol intake. Hepatic manifestations were assessed based on the following symptoms and signs:

Symptoms: Loss of appetite (anorexia), fatigue, malaise, right upper quadrant discomfort, upper GI bleeding (hematemesis/melena), and abdominal distension.

Signs: Hepatomegaly, splenomegaly, and signs of portal hypertension.

Investigations

- All patients underwent the following laboratory investigations:
- Complete hemogram
- Blood sugar (fasting and postprandial)
- Renal function tests
- Urine routine and microscopic examination
- Liver function tests (Serum bilirubin, SGOT/SGPT, PT (INR), S. protein)
- Lipid profile
- Electrolytes (Na⁺, K⁺, Ca⁺⁺)
- Abdominal ultrasonography to assess liver size, shape, and echotexture, diagnose NAFLD and NASH, and exclude other causes of chronic liver disease.

Patients with abnormal liver function tests were subjected to additional investigations to rule out other causes:

- Serological markers for HBV and HCV
- Autoimmune markers

Laboratory Methods

10 ml of blood was drawn in EDTA and sterile vials under complete antiseptic and aseptic

measures for examination. Hematology and biochemistry tests were performed using the following principles:

- CBC estimation by electronic resistance (impedance) and light scattering principle.
- Cell counting by Coulter principle.
- Liver function tests and kidney function tests by enzymatic assay and flow cytometry.
- Blood sugar estimation by hexokinase method using optical impedance.

Result

The study included 100 patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus, and the results highlight significant findings regarding hepatic dysfunction in these patients. The study had more female participants (58%) than male (42%), with the majority of patients being between 40-60 years old. 64% of patients had controlled diabetes, while 36% had uncontrolled diabetes.

Table 1: Demographic profile

Parameters	Values (%)
Age Group (years)	
30-39	4%
40-49	38%
50-59	42%
>60	16%
Gender	
Male	42%
Female	58%

Table 2: Control Status of Diabetes Mellitus

Control Status	Male	Female	Total
Controlled	21	43	64%
Uncontrolled	21	15	36%

Most patients (43%) had diabetes for less than 5 years, followed by those with 5-9 years (41%) and more than 10 years (16%).

Table 3: Duration of Diabetes Mellitus

Duration (years)	Male	Female	Total
0-4	19	24	43%
5-9	20	21	41%
>10	3	13	16%

The majority of patients were asymptomatic (57%), while others exhibited symptoms like fatigue/malaise (39%), anorexia (27%), and RUQ discomfort (24%). Hepatomegaly was observed in 25% of patients.

Table 4: Prevalence of Symptoms of Hepatic Involvement

Symptoms	Male	Female	Total
Asymptomatic	24	33	57%
Anorexia	12	15	27%
Fatigue/malaise	17	22	39%
RUQ Discomfort	8	16	24%

Table 5: Prevalence of Signs of Hepatic Involvement

Signs	Male	Female	Total
No Sign	30	39	69%
Hepatomegaly	8	17	25%
Icterus	3	7	10%
Ascites	5	5	10%
UGI bleeding	1	2	3%

Abnormal LFTs were noted in a significant portion of patients, with elevated levels of serum bilirubin, AST, ALT, and prothrombin time.

Table 6: Abnormal Liver Function Tests

LFTs	Total
Mean Serum Bilirubin	2.5
Mean AST	59.2
Mean ALT	51.5
Mean Prothrombin time	24.2
Mean S. albumin	2.2

34% of patients showed increased hepatic echogenicity, indicating fatty liver changes.

Table 7: Hepatic Ultrasonographic Findings

USG Findings	Total
Normal	66%
Increased hepatic echogenicity	34%

The risk of NAFLD increased with the duration of diabetes, with higher instances of hepatomegaly, abnormal LFTs, and abnormal USG findings in patients with longer diabetes duration.

Table 8: Risk of NAFLD in Diabetes Mellitus According to Duration of Diabetes

Duration of Diabetes (years)	Hepatomegaly	Abnormal LFTs	Abnormal USG
<5	3	13	9
5-9	15	19	16
>10	7	13	9

Discussion

The sample comprised 100 patients, predominantly female (58%), with a male-to-female ratio of 2:3. The age distribution revealed that most patients were between 40 and 60 years old, with the mean age of males being 51.0 years and females 51.3 years. This demographic suggests that middle-aged individuals are more susceptible to hepatic complications in diabetes.

Control of diabetes among the study participants was notably varied. A significant majority, 64%, had controlled blood glucose levels, while 36% had uncontrolled diabetes. This differentiation is crucial as it impacts the prevalence and severity of hepatic dysfunction.

The duration of diabetes in the study group varied, with 43% of patients having diabetes for less than 5 years, 41% for 5-9 years, and 16% for more than 10 years. Notably, hepatic dysfunction symptoms and signs were more prevalent in patients with a longer duration of diabetes. The most common symptom was fatigue or malaise (39%), followed by anorexia (27%) and right upper quadrant discomfort (24%). Hepatomegaly was the most frequently observed sign, present in 25% of patients, indicating liver enlargement.

Liver function tests (LFTs) provided further insights into the hepatic status of the patients. Elevated serum bilirubin, AST, ALT, and prothrombin time were observed in a substantial portion of the patients, suggesting impaired liver function. Specifically, 20% had elevated serum bilirubin levels, 33% had increased AST, and 32% had elevated ALT. These biochemical markers are indicative of liver cell injury and dysfunction.

Ultrasonographic findings were consistent with the biochemical data. While 66% of patients had normal liver ultrasound results, 34% showed increased hepatic echogenicity, a hallmark of fatty liver changes. This finding aligns with the observed prevalence of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) among the patients.

The risk of developing NAFLD was found to be correlated with the duration of diabetes. Patients with a diabetes duration of more than 5 years exhibited a higher prevalence of hepatomegaly, abnormal LFTs, and abnormal ultrasound findings compared to those with a shorter duration of diabetes. Specifically, hepatomegaly was present in 43.8% of patients with diabetes for over 10 years, compared to only 6.9% in those with less than 5 years of diabetes. This trend underscores the progressive nature of hepatic complications in long-term diabetes.

The results of this study underscore the significant prevalence of hepatic dysfunction in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, particularly as the duration of diabetes increases. The findings highlight the importance of regular monitoring and early detection of liver abnormalities in diabetic patients. The high prevalence of asymptomatic hepatic involvement suggests that routine screening with liver function tests and ultrasonography should be considered in the management of diabetes.

The correlation between longer diabetes duration and increased risk of NAFLD indicates that chronic hyperglycemia and associated metabolic disturbances contribute to liver damage. Effective glycemic control appears to be crucial in mitigating these risks, as evidenced by the lower prevalence of hepatic dysfunction in patients with controlled diabetes.

A study examined mitochondrial dysfunction across organ systems in type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). The study highlighted that hyperglycemia and insulin resistance lead to mitochondrial dysfunction, affecting hepatocyte metabolism. This results in hepatocellular injury due to the accumulation of mitochondrial DNA mutations and depletion of mtDNA copy numbers, contributing to the progression of hepatic dysfunction [6].

A case-control study was conducted to determine the association between MASLD and T2DM. The study found that 47.9% of diabetic patients had MASLD compared to 33.7% of non-diabetic

controls. Elevated serum aspartate transaminase (AST) and alanine transaminase (ALT) levels were significantly associated with MASLD, emphasizing the importance of regular screening for hepatic dysfunction in T2DM patients [7].

A study explored the extent of liver dysfunction in T2DM patients. The study found elevated levels of liver enzymes (AST, ALT, ALP) in 46-62% of patients and fatty liver changes in 17.39% of the participants. These findings suggest that hepatic dysfunction is prevalent among T2DM patients and can be used as an indirect marker of insulin resistance [8].

A study assessed the efficacy and safety of luseogliflozin in T2DM patients with hepatic dysfunction. Over 52 weeks, significant reductions were observed in AST, ALT, γ -GTP, HbA1c, body weight, and fasting plasma glucose. The study concluded that luseogliflozin is effective in improving hepatic function and reducing liver fat in T2DM patients [9].

A study reviewed the complex relationship between NAFLD and T2DM, focusing on insulin resistance as a key pathological link. The study highlighted that hepatic insulin resistance exacerbates T2DM, leading to more severe liver complications such as cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. The review emphasized the need for targeted treatments to address the intertwined pathophysiological mechanisms [10].

Conclusion

This study emphasizes the need for a comprehensive approach to managing diabetes, which includes vigilant monitoring for hepatic complications. Early intervention and appropriate management strategies can potentially prevent the progression of liver disease in diabetic patients, thereby improving overall health outcomes.

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